

STRAIN FIELD CHARACTERIZATION OF FILAMENT WINDING PATTERN AT $\pm 55^\circ$ USING NUMERICAL IMAGE CORRELATION

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SUMMARY

This research has for aim to analyze the mechanical behavior of unit cells of filament wound helical pattern at $\pm 55^\circ$ using flat specimens, by measuring the displacement field obtained by numerical image correlation. The main objective is to evaluate the strains at different zones of the pattern in order to know the failure sequence and modes.

Keywords: filament winding, unit cells, image correlation, strain field.

I. INTRODUCTION

The structural behavior of fiber wound composites (FWC) has been investigated by testing the complete specimens under the service conditions [1, 3, 4, 6, 12], with the aim to observe and predict the failure mechanisms and the cracking sequence. Nevertheless, due to the difficulty to reproduce in laboratory the real conditions, this kind of tests require specific equipment, which in most of the cases increase the cost and research time. These difficulties also exist for computational simulations, because the modeling of very complex structures has an impact in the time processing of the algorithms.

With the objective to test FWC with simplified methods, it is necessary to design representative flat specimens that include their characteristic winding pattern, which can be tested in conventional machines. The structural behavior of FWC at constituting cell level with flat specimens is studied until now [2, 5], in order to generalize the mechanical response of FWC. The study of crack initiation and propagation in simplified specimens with an optical technique, such as numerical image correlation (DIC) [7-11, 13], will allow a first comprehension of fracture phenomena.

Recently, the researchers of Institut Clément Ader (ICA) [1, 7-9, 12, 13] invest their efforts studying the pattern influence in FWC mechanical response. They compare experimental results with analytical and numerical models in order to predict their failure modes. These predictions have the interest for calculating FWC strength as a function of the material properties, service loads, environment and crack size.

With this background, the aim of this work is to obtain the characteristic FWC strain field using a flat specimen and DIC technique in a conventional tensile test. The first part of the paper explains the experimental set up. The second one compares the DIC results with FEM simulations. Third part deals with fractographic examination in order to infer the failure mechanisms. Finally, the paper ends with the concluding remarks.

II. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Fabrication of winding pattern flat specimens

The first attempts to fabricate winding pattern flat specimens are carried out in order to obtain representative specimens of FWC with their unit cells. Composite are fabricated with E-glass rovings and EPOLAM 2015 resin. Pre-forms are made with a pattern of $\pm 55^\circ$, 15 rovings per unit cell and two plies of thickness [12] as is show in Fig. 1-a. The vacuum bagging process is implemented following the repairing recommended practices manual of a Mexican airline. The vacuum is fixed at 0.2 atm (absolute pressure) for 2 hrs and the polymerization reaction take place for 16 hrs at 25 °C. Once the composite plates are ready, specimens with two unit cells are cut following the axial and hoop direction of pattern as are shown in Fig. 1-b. Unit cells dimensions for $\pm 55^\circ$ helical pattern configuration are presented in Fig. 1-c.

2.2 Physical and mechanical characterization of winding pattern at $\pm 55^\circ$

Physical characterization is done according to ASTM D2584 procedure, in order to determine composite density. Fiber volume fraction, matrix volume fraction and void content are calculated with burn-off method, following the standard ASTM D3171. Mechanical characterization is carried out with normalized procedure announced in ASTM D3039. In order to calculate the mechanical properties of helical pattern, strain gages are glued in the stratified zone and in the fiber undulation zone of the pattern. Physical and mechanical characterizations are summarized in Table 1.

Fig. 1. Helical pattern composite, a) Pre-form with filament winding pattern, b) Specimens at hoop and axial direction of the pattern, c) Unit cell dimensions.

Table 1. Physical and mechanical properties for filament winding pattern at $\pm 55^\circ$.

Composite Density	ρ (g/cm ³)	1.845
Fiber Volume Fraction	V_f	0.57
Matrix Volume Fraction	V_m	0.39
Void content	V_p	0.04
Hoop Elastic Modulus	E_h (GPa)	10.7
Axial Elastic Modulus	E_a (GPa)	5.7
Hoop Poisson Ratio	ν_h	0.75
Axial Poisson Ratio	ν_a	0.25
In-plane Shear Modulus	G_{ah} (GPa)	2.75

2.3 Tensile test and image correlation set up

First, photographs of both faces of each specimen are taken to identify existing defects in the unit cells. Specimens are painted with a black/white random speckled blueprint and the CCD camera set is placed and calibrated for making the images acquisition.

The loading pass for the tensile tests is made manually; each 300 N of load an image is captured. Tests are finished until the rupture of the specimen, when main crack is notoriously evident. The different stages for tensile test set up are illustrated in Fig. 2.

Once the images are captured, the software VIC3D[®] is used to measure the existing displacements at each level of load. Initial image without load is designed as reference image. DIC depends of two parameters, the “*subset*” which controls the dimension of the selected surface to follow the displacements and the “*step*” which controls the space between the analyzed points during the correlation. The parameters used are subset 15 / step 5 [13]. This means that analyzed surface has 15 pixels per side and each 5 pixels the displacements are measured. For performing the images correlation, the Quantic B Spline Interpolation is used. The Zero Normalized Quadratic Differences criterion, which is not function of the distance or intensity of light source, is implemented [13].

Fig. 2. Set up for images correlation, a) Specimen with random speckled blueprint, b) Images correlation tensile test, c) Specimen rupture, d) Strain field for winding pattern.

2.4 Numerical simulation for strain field of winding pattern at $\pm 55^\circ$

With the purpose of completing a three-part comparison for strain field in FWC unit cells, a numerical simulation is made using finite element method (FEM). The FEM model is made with ANSYS[™] software, respecting nominal dimensions of unit cell. The stratified and wound zones are indicated following the ply-sequence of composite with non-linear shell elements (SHELL91). The model for the specimen cut in the axial direction has 1396 tetrahedral elements with 2865 nodes; the model for the specimen in hoop direction has 1172 tetrahedral elements with 2369. For the boundary conditions, specimens are fixed at the bottom and loaded above, according to load increments from tensile tests. The post-processing will show the longitudinal principal strain (e_1) at the different zones of the FWC unit cell.

III. RESULTS

3.1 Determination of strain field of winding pattern at $\pm 55^\circ$

Load-strain curves for the winding pattern at $\pm 55^\circ$ are drawn with the aim of comparing the strain measurements by images correlation and the ones obtained by strain gages and FEM simulations. The longitudinal principal strain (e_1) for axial and hoop directions is plotted in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4, respectively. The average slope in the elastic domain (0-300 $\mu\epsilon$) is almost the same for the three measure techniques. After that, variations of strain come out until the rupture, showing a non-linear response.

Fig. 3. Load-strain curve for FWC flat specimens in the axial direction.

Fig. 4. Load-strain curve for FWC flat specimens in the hoop direction.

The photographs collected during the tests show over-strain localization in the specimens. For the axial direction specimens, the over-strain zones are localized in the helical cross zone. Mean while, for the hoop direction, the over-strain zone are confined in the stratified zone of the unit cells. The images exhibit that the initial over-strain region is confined in the lateral side of the unit cells. Both of the helical wound zone and the stratified zone show evidence of the strain concentration along the fiber alignment. The global strain field (e_1) of unit cells in each direction, confirming the progression of the over-strain localization, is detailed in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Strain field for filament winding pattern at $\pm 55^\circ$ in the axial and hoop direction.

3.2 Fractographic examination

Axial specimens exhibit fracture surfaces in the surroundings of unit cells. The zone of helical-cross shows interface separation, meanwhile the wound zone suffers pattern angular distortion, because the fibers were found rotated and broken. The stratified zone shows delamination. All these evidences are presented in Fig. 6-a. On the other part, the hoop specimens also have main cracks in the cell perimeter. In the wound zone, the interface breakup is clearly distinguished. The delamination of stratified zone extends itself from the center to the sides of the unit cell. All these statements are indicated in Fig. 6-b. The micro-scale fractographic examination is carried out by SEM. Micrographs from the fracture surface are taken with the aim to infer the main fracture mechanisms. Micrographs are taken from the stratified zone. Matrix granular rupture and fiber fragmentation are evident in the stratified zone as is illustrated in Fig. 7.

Fig. 6. Fractographic examination for specimens in the a) Axial and b) Hoop directions.

Fig. 7. SEM Micrographs of fracture surface in the stratified zone.

3.3 FEM simulations for strain field of winding pattern cells

Numerical simulations for strain field (e_I) of winding pattern cells are shown in Fig. 8. Simulations, as the images correlation, show an over-strain localization as well in the cross helical zone as in the stratified zone of the unit cells.

Fig.8 FEM results for longitudinal strain field, showing over-strain in unit cells.

IV. DISCUSSION

Filament winding specimens in axial and hoop direction show a linear behavior in the elastic domain ($0 - 3000 \mu\epsilon$) and a non-linear response after this point until the fracture is reached. The non-linear behavior has for characteristic the localization of over-strain zones in the composite. The winding pattern gets its maximum strength and loses it gradually due to the nucleation and growth of cracks in the cells within (see Fig. 3 & 4).

The strength of filament winding pattern in hoop direction is bigger than the one observed in the axial direction of the pattern. The hoop/axial strength average ratio ($\sigma_{hoop}/\sigma_{ax}$) is 2.2 in the elastic domain. The ratio is calculated by dividing the strength of hoop specimens over the strength of axial specimens in the elastic domain. This ratio is 90% close to the biaxial condition for tubes under internal pressure with end effect. However, this condition is not available in the non-linear domain, for the reason that the failure modes have influence in the mechanical response of the winding flat composite.

Fracture sequence of the winding pattern specimens starts with a crack in the lateral corner of the unit cell. The crack runs into the interlaminar zones and it causes delamination which extends through the stratified and wound zones (see Fig. 9-c and Fig. 10-c). After this, the plies of helical cross zone start to slide because a combined failure crack mode (shear in Mode II and III), resulting in the interface breakup and the matrix rupture. After that, the no-embedded fibers rotate and try to align themselves into the load direction. Finally, fibers rupture occurs by cleavage and the failure of winding composite is complete.

Because of the specimens had certain defects in the ply along the thickness and misalignments in the superposition of hoop zone, the pattern is not well aligned to the direction of load. This discrepancy of fibers, attributed to the manufacture procedure, aids to crack nucleation in the corner of the cell. Furthermore, the presence of a zone rich in resin and zones with deficient impregnation caused low adherence between matrix and reinforcement which facilitated the crack propagation.

Fig. 9. Qualitative comparison of the hoop winding specimens and their fracture zones.
a) Image correlation technique, b) FEM simulation.

Fig. 10. Qualitative comparison of the axial specimens and their fracture zones.
 a) Image correlation technique and b) FEM simulation.

The failure mechanism is identified as interface breakup with matrix-fiber separation and matrix pulverization, which is noticeable because numerous matrix particles are sprinkled in the crack surface. Also, the fibers are broken by cleavage (see Fig. 7).

The crack path and the crack sequence described above seem to be very similar to those visualized in the buckling behavior of FWC cylinders [1, 12]. In these works, it is remarked that the damage zones correspond to those where the FWC tube is over-deformed. FWC tube fracture zones are in the perimeter of unit cell and in the stratified zone. Nevertheless, more precise tests should be performed in order to establish a relevant link between the failure modes for FWC flat specimens and for FWC cylinders.

CONCLUSIONS

The filament winding pattern specimens in hoop direction exhibited a higher strength than those with the cells in axial direction. The hoop/axial strength ratio (2.2:1) is very close to the theoretical biaxial condition of tubes under internal pressure with end effect.

Crack path starts at lateral side and it runs into the center of the unit cells. Main failure mechanism in FWC flat specimens is interface breakup. A mixed failure mode (shear in Mode II & III) is responsible for the damage within the cells. The analyzed damage seems to be very similar to FWC thick & thin walled cylinders buckling [1, 12].

DIC strain field values, strain gages measures and FEM simulations show good accuracy in the elastic domain. However, strain variations are observed in the non-linear domain. The proposed methodology could be used to have a first understanding of FWC unit cells behavior, so FWC complex structure testing can be carry out successfully.

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